

Video Laryngoscopy an Alternative to FOB for Securing the Airway of Retrosternal Goiter in a Reactive Airway Disease Patient: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Patients presenting with retrosternal goitre always pose a challenge in securing the airway. Fiberoptic intubation despite being the gold standard requires expertise training, availability at all centres with increased exposure to the lower airway. Computed tomography (CT) scan provides accurate information on the extent of the goitre in aid to the surrounding compression, a comprehensive preoperative assessment can help plan to secure a difficult airway giving an alternative plan to use of fiberoptic intubation.

Keywords: Computed tomography scan, Difficult airway, Fiberoptic intubation, Retrosternal goitre, Tracheal compression, Video laryngoscopy.

INTRODUCTION

^[1]The degree & extent of enlarged thyroid gland causes displacement and compression of trachea and surrounding blood vessels. The symptoms may range from dyspnoea to position changes, predisposing these patients to further lower airway reactive diseases & frequent upper respiratory tract infections. ^[2] This leads to challenges for the anesthesiologist as a difficult to ventilate and intubate case scenario. ^[3] Therefore, adequate assessment of the extent of the retrosternal goitre and the degree of tracheal compression is important part of the preoperative assessment. ^[4] Computed tomography (CT) scan gives an accurate measurement of the narrowest tracheal diameter at the site of compression along with the details of tracheal deviation and compression of other structures. Here we present a case report with tracheal deviation and compression airway was secured using video laryngoscopy following the CT findings preoperatively and fiberoptic was avoided giving us an alternative plan.

CASE HISTORY

A 67-year-old, gentleman presented with complaints of incidental swelling in the neck gradually increased since 3 months to the current size followed by hoarseness of voice and difficulty in deglutition since 1 month, known case of hypertension and bronchial asthma on nebulisations.

On examination, a firm and immobile swelling measuring approximately 7 x 8 cms. The lower border was not palpable. The swelling moved with deglutition. There was no movement of swelling with protrusion of tongue.

HRCT Chest : Retrosternal extension of the swelling was noted with compression of trachea along with deviation to the right compression and minimum tracheal diameter of 6.2 mm at the narrowest point. There was ? positive lymphadenopathy and vessels were normal. Laboratory examination and thyroid function test were wnl, pulmonary function test showed: Moderate restrictive pattern with poor reversibility to bronchodilators, Indirect laryngoscopy : left vocal cord paralysis was noted, Ecg: rbbb with 1-2 vpc sinus tachycardia.

2D ECHO: EF 60%, wnl

CXR: Bilateral lower lobe haziness with? right lower lobe opacity ? microaspirations Trachea deviated to the right

Patient was planned for intraoperative neuromonitoring with total thyroidectomy & sternotomy.

Preoperatively Procedure was explained to the patient and relatives with high risk consent , MDT approach undertaken with pulmonologist with proper antibiotic coverage for 10 days and icu backup kept. Upon arrival in the operation theatre, ASA graded standard monitors were attached : ECG, NIBP, SPO2, capnography, BIS electrodes attached.

Difficult airway trolley with fiberoptic bronchoscopes, IgeL, I-l=Lma, working suctions, FONA equipment kept ready. 2 peripheral wide bore on upperlimb secured .Patient was kept supine with 10 degree head elevation and table tilted to left 5 degree , Preoxygenation with 6l o2 via Hudson mask started , inj dexmetomidine (2mcg/ml) started at 0.8 ml/kg/hr, At the outset, 10 mg Ketamine and 30 mcg fentanyl, 60 mg preservative free lignocaine iv, paracetamol 1000 mg , tramadol 50 mg , dexamethasone 8 mg with 100 mg hydrocortisone ,1 mg midazolam administered, a preliminary awake laryngoscopy using C-MAC® video-laryngoscope (Karl Storz Endoscopy-America, CA, USA) revealed a vocal cord visualisation with left cord immobility and right cord mobile. Subsequently 150 mg propofol titrated gradually, observing with BIS : 40 and confirming mask ventilation on capnography , 75 mg succinylcholine administered ,a C-MAC® video-laryngoscope no: 4 (Karl Storz Endoscopy-America, CA, CL GRADE 3 using an armored NIMS endotracheal tube (size 7.0 internal diameter) which was advanced over the Eschmann stylet and with the contact surface over the vocal cords without any difficulty. Confirmation was done by auscultation of the bilateral breath sounds and capnography. Patient was kept on TIVA with maintenance : inj dexmetomidine(0.5 mcg/ml/kg/hr) and TCI propofol(10mg/kg) MARSH model started, no inhalational agent used, no long acting muscle relaxant used , ventilatory parameters: (PCV-VG TV: 400, RR; 14, FIO2: 0.4, PEEP;6) O2 + AIR

BIS kept around 40-60, intraoperative left recurrent laryngeal nerve monitoring done , intermittent fentanyl doses of 2 mcg/ml were given to respond to surgical stress responses , The intraoperative procedure was uneventful , I/o: 2000 plasmalyte with urine : 1200 ml blood loss : 300 ml noted , hgt: 133 mg/dl , Post procedure cuff leak test done which showed leak +, A CHECK DLscopy done : left vocal cord immobile+ , right cord mobile+ ,after returning to spontaneous ventilation over an airway exchange catheter the patient was extubated, with mild titrated doses of esmolol 1 mg/kg to blunt extubation response.

Patient was kept in ICU 24hrs for observation.

Figure 1: HRCT of Chest

Figure 2: X-RAY CHEST

DISCUSSION

^[5] Though fiberoptic bronchoscopy is the gold standard for intubation ^[6] but in patients with wheezing or airway obstruction, the fiberoptic bronchoscope procedure may impede and cause reactive airway. Therefore, the application of this technique in patients with severe tracheal obstruction is controversial. ^[7] Bennett et al.

reported that only 6 out of 1,969 patients undergoing thyroid surgery had difficult airways for tracheal intubation. [8] In another study by Gilfillan et al., of the patients expected to have difficult airways preoperatively, 87% patients were successfully intubated under direct laryngoscopy. [9] In the study by Pan et al., all patients completed tracheal intubation with video laryngoscopy, even cases with tracheal diameter of less than 1 cm. [10] Thus, careful preoperative assessment may enable the anesthesiologist to intubate the patient under video laryngoscopy and avoid the use of fiberoptic intubation. CT scan is highly valuable in the preoperative evaluation of the patient as it gives accurate details about the thyroid size, the extent of the swelling in the substernal and mediastinal regions and the extent of invasion into surrounding tissues [11,12]

CONCLUSION

Preoperative CT scan is vital in patients with retrosternal goitre, planned for thyroidectomy. Careful assessment of the deviation of trachea and compression of the surrounding structures can help in proper planning to secure the airway while minimizing the need of procedures like fiberoptic intubation which can help to avoid further manipulation over a lower airway reactive disease patient.

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